

The Role of Air Cargo Between Air Transport Development and Environmental Sustainability

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Article Info	Abstract
RESEARCH ARTICLE	Development of air transport is important for trade, competitiveness, and growth of the economies. For trade to be competitive, continued investment to improve air transport infrastructure is necessary for meeting increasing demand for air cargo providing fast deliveries of high value and time sensitive goods. While the development of air transport and air cargo is beneficial for the economy, it has negative consequences on environment. For environment to be sustainable, development of air transport and air cargo has an important role to play. This study therefore aims to find out what effect the development of air transport has on environmental sustainability and on this effect what role air cargo plays. Based on the Baron & Kenny mediator analysis, cross country data set was tested by multiple regression and Sobel test. The results show that the development of air transport has a negative effect on environmental sustainability and on this effect air cargo is a partial mediator. By introducing air cargo as a mediator in the relationship, the negative effect of air transport development on environmental sustainability weakens but its significance remains.
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1. Introduction

Air cargo transportation plays a critical role in the trade and competitiveness of countries. To be competitive, timely and reliable delivery of goods in the international markets are increasingly important. This in turn strengthens the role of air cargo among the other transportation modes. In fact, 35 percent of world trade in terms of value is now transported by air cargo, and it is revealed that a 1 percent improvement in the connectivity of air cargo increases the world exports and the imports by 6.3 percent. As the sector grows, the trade and competitiveness strengthen. In line with its growing importance, International Air Transport Association (IATA) predicts a significant rise in the air cargo traffic in the upcoming period (IATA, 2023). This level of increase obviously requires a larger investment in the development of air transport infrastructure – growth and expansion of aircrafts, airports, terminals, runways, equipment and, vehicles to name but a few. While the development and investment in such a scale is beneficial for the economic and social wellbeing, it is counterproductive to the sustainability of the environment. The extent of such an expansion of activities poses serious risks to natural resources and climate.

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The industry recognizes its significant role on the impact and takes important initiatives to reduce it. Cargo airlines as well as airports through their representative bodies - International Air Cargo Association (TIACA) and Airport Council International (ACI) – respectively rolled out a road map outlining key criteria to decarbonize air transportation. While former focus more on sustainable aviation fuels, energy efficiency and optimization; the latter more on renewable energy purchases, on site thermal decarbonization and renewables (TIACA, 2021; ACI, 2022).

Therefore, this study aims to investigate to what extent air transport development (ATD) has an impact on environmental sustainability (ENV) and what role air cargo ton-km (CTK) plays in this impact. In the first part of the study, the definition of the concepts in the research model and the background of the study are explained. In the second part, hypotheses are developed. In the third part, the research model and method are presented. In the fourth part, sampling and measurements are explained. In the fifth part, hypotheses are tested, and the results are analyzed. In the last part, conclusions are drawn, and evaluations are made.

2. Theoretical Background

Air cargo transportation plays an important role in the trade and economic growth of countries. The competitiveness in trade is more and more depends on the speed and the quality of services surrounding the goods presented to the international markets. Among those services, transportation fulfils one of the basic needs and crucial functions in market entry and access. Having timely and faster delivery of high value added and time-sensitive goods is a prerequisite for competitiveness. This obligation increases the importance of the air cargo, for which it has an absolute advantage in international transportation. In fact, now up to 35 percent of world trade in goods value is transported by air cargo (Bartle et al., 2021). It is revealed that a 1 percent of improvement in air cargo connectivity translates into 6.3 percent increase in total world trade (TIACA, 2021). In contrast, a one-day delay goods in transit causes a cost increase which is equivalent to a customs tariff of 0.6 to 2.3 percent (Hummels & Schaur, 2012). Given the effects at this magnitude, the significant growth predictions of air cargo traffic – that is made by international organizations well into the future – should not be surprising (IATA, 2023).

Figure 1 shows that air cargo traffic has been on a continuous rise since 1990, reaching in 2021 up to a total of 219 million tons-km for the world, up to 9.3 million tons-km for Türkiye:

Fig. 1: Air cargo ton-km (World Bank, World Development Indicators, 2023).

Figure 2 on the other hand shows the increase in cargo traffic only in tons, excluding the distance flown for the years from 2013 to 2022. The upward trend is still prevalent especially in the international routes:

Fig. 2: Air cargo ton-km by Turkish Airports (State Airports Authority – DHMİ Türkiye, 2023).

Figure 3 this time shows the traffic increase in number of air flights both in domestic and international routes – which dropped to 853,750 air flights in 2020, but recovered a year followed in 2021 and continued to its increasing trend from there onwards:

Fig. 3: Number of Air Flights in Turkish Airports (State Airports Authority – DHMİ Türkiye, 2023).

These apparent significant increases in both number of air flights and air cargo traffic naturally necessitate a continuous development of the extensiveness and condition of air transport infrastructure. As a matter of fact, table 1 shows that the total number of airports to meet such increased demand and traffic, jumped from 26 in 2003 to 55 in 2021, being doubled up in the last twenty years:

Table 1: Türkiye airports and air cargo statistics

	2003	2021	2025 (forecast)
Airports	26	55	-
Air Flights	218405	466266	882780
Air Cargo (ton)	198347	1604833	1646122
Air Cargo (ton km)	1 million	9,3 million	-

Source: World Bank and State Airports Authority - DHMİ, Türkiye, 2023

In addition, table 1 also shows that traffic in terms of cargo-tons has increased by more than eightfold. Parallel to this remarkable past record, the number of flights is also predicted to double in 2025 reaching over 882 thousand. This upward trend in the world as well as in Türkiye verifies the need of a continuous development of air transport infrastructure both in terms of its extensiveness and its condition.

However, while such development is obviously beneficial for the economic development, it has adverse effects on environmental sustainability. Sustainability is essentially evaluated in three main areas, namely environmental, economic, and human/social – often cited as ‘triple bottom line’ in the literature. In each area, the performances of the countries are evaluated and ranked. According to this ranking, 0 indicates a poor, 5 a medium and 10 a strong performance. Figure 4 shows the overall performance of these areas between 2006

and 2019 in which environmental sustainability did not improve and lagged significantly behind human/social sustainability:

Fig. 4: World Sustainability Indicators Triple Bottomline (*Sustainable Society Index, 2023*).

Environmental sustainability itself consists of two basic categories. One is natural resources, and the other one is energy and climate. Figure 5 shows that the overall performance of countries in both categories remained also stagnant and did not show any improvement whatsoever:

Fig. 5: World Sustainability Indicators, Environmental Sustainability (*Sustainable Society Index, 2023*).

There may surely be many factors playing a role on the deterioration of environment in the past decades but with its increased rate of past growth so far together with its similar projection well into the future, the role of air transportation on that impact is and remains to be highly significant. This impact is also well recognized by the industry as well as researchers in the literature and efforts are put in place to reduce it if not to eliminate.

The cargo airlines sector recognizes its critical role on carbon emission and has adopted a road map to mitigate it (TIACA, 2021). Main priorities – set out in this map to decarbonize the sector – are centered mainly around the criteria of a transition from fossil fuel to sustainable aviation fuel (SAF), of relying more on renewable energy sources as well as of gaining efficiency in operation. These priorities are also compatible with the findings in the literature: While being critical of its achievability within the targeted period, the most recent research in the field is unified behind the fact that – comparing to other criteria in decarbonization – SAF has the greatest potential in reducing the emission. ICAO (2022:34) puts this potentiality as high as eighty per cent (ICAO, 2022; Zhao et al., 2021; Prussi et al., 2021; Abrantes et al., 2021; Lau, 2022; Cracknell et al., 2023; Kok et al., 2021). However, that does not mean that the efforts to maintain efficiency, reliance on the other renewable energy sources, and the development of technology are anyhow less important and should be abandoned. Quite the contrary, only the combined effects of the criteria and necessary efforts would produce

an aspired outcome on the targets set out in the roadmap (Hasan et al., 2021; Ekici & Sevinc 2022; Saini et al., 2023; Yu & See, 2023).

The airport sector, like the airlines, also sees energy and emission management as vitally important for its sustainability. However, due to the structural differences, its main priorities in the carbon emission reduction vary. In their decarbonization road map put out by Airports Council International (ACI), airports focus more on the areas of purchased fuel, heating, lighting, generators, ground service equipment making sure that the power used by them is to come from renewable energy sources (ACI, 2022). Current findings in the literature support these priorities: Energy usage and emission reduction targets are of critical factors for the sustainability of airports in the long term (Sreenath et al, 2021); a small delay in the time spent on the ground causes considerable level of energy consumption (Gladys et al., 2022); electrification and optimization of ground service equipment is important in emission reduction (Ahmadi & Akgündüz, 2023); new airport projects and expansions around the high-income cities causes higher emissions (Xiong et al, 2023).

Revealing the critical role of air transport on emissions and mitigation efforts underlined by the industry as well as the current research in the literature, this study aims to investigate to what extent the development of air transport infrastructure influences environmental sustainability and what role air cargo traffic plays in this relationship. Based on this field literature and theoretical background, we can now move on to the next stage of developing hypotheses amongst variables in the research model.

3. Hypothesis Development

The hypotheses are now developed as follows to reflect the binary relationship of the variables based on the related literature.

3.1. Air Transport Development and Air Cargo

Air transportation and trade grows faster than gross domestic product (GDP) (Belobaba et al., 2016; Morrell & Klein, 2019). These force air cargo traffic to rise both in terms of tons and ton-km (IATA, 2023, DHMI, 2023). Rising traffic in air cargo in turn requires a rapid development of air transport infrastructure. Long-term-strategic investments undertaken to develop infrastructure play an important role in the economic development of countries (Graham, 2023). In addition, countries investing in their infrastructure improve air connectivity and therefore their logistics performance. Countries that strengthen their logistics performance in turn have a higher rate of trade and economic growth (Çelebi, 2015, 2018, 2021, 2022). Therefore, to meet higher traffic and performance demands, air transportation infrastructure needs to be developed on a continuous basis. In the light of these explanations, the following first hypothesis is reached:

H₁: Air transport development positively affect air cargo.

3.2. Air Cargo and Environmental Sustainability

While the increase in air cargo traffic generally brings positive effects on economic and human/social welfare, it has serious adverse effects on environmental sustainability. The rise in air cargo traffic increases fossil fuel consumption and carbon dioxide emissions as a result. In fact, 15 percent of total greenhouse gas emissions worldwide come from the transportation in general (Larson, 2021) and the share of commercial aviation corresponds to 3 percent, of which 19 percent coming directly from air cargo (Graver et al., 2019). In the light of these studies, the following second hypothesis is determined.

H₂: Air cargo negatively affects environmental sustainability.

3.2. Air transport development and Environmental Sustainability

To increase the extensiveness and the condition of air transport infrastructure is beneficial in bringing economies of scale, scope, and density to reduce unit costs. However, the growth of facilities on the other hand makes air transportation systems and operations more complex. Especially the increase in the number of air terminals and facilities makes the coordination of services difficult and cause a high level of repetition, moving away from being then a simple operation to that of a heavier and cumbersome one. The increase in distance between different facilities delays and complicates access, ultimately bringing negative effects on environmental sustainability (Graham, 2023). To eliminate these negative effects though, the International

Airport Council (ACI) has developed a carbon accreditation program, and an increasing number of airports – currently a total of 291 – are subscribed now completing various stages (ACI, 2023).

H₃: Air transport development negatively affects environmental sustainability.

3.4. The role of Air Cargo between Air Transport Development and Environmental Sustainability

The development of air transportation is important for trade and competitiveness. For trade to be competitive, rapid delivery of high value and time-sensitive products worldwide is a must. The need of faster deliveries naturally increases demand for air cargo. Higher demand for air cargo necessitates the development of air transportation as a result. This positive inter-relationship between air cargo and air transport development turns into virtuous circle benefiting economic growth and development. But it quickly becomes a vicious one once the environment has been included into the picture. To overcome the negative effect on environment, airports recognize their role in the reduction of carbon emissions and subscribe to international accreditation programs outlined earlier. (ACI, 2023). In line with these explanations, the following final hypothesis is reached.

H₄: Air cargo is a mediator between air transport development and environmental sustainability.

4. Methodology

This study was analyzed according to Baron & Kenny research methodology (1986). This method attempts to reveal to what extent the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable occurs through the role of another variable defined as being the mediator variable. Determining this role in the relationship between the dependent and independent variables requires primarily the fulfillment of the following conditions:

- i) A change in the independent variable causes a change in the mediator variable,
- ii) A change in the mediator variable causes a change in the dependent variable,
- iii) When mediator and independent variables are included in the analysis together, the previous significant effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable should decrease or become insignificant and disappear completely.

Figure 5 shows the conceptual model of the research. Hierarchical regression method was used to test the hypotheses.

Fig. 5: Research Model (Author).

ATD, CTK and ENV are the variables of the research model, and three regression equations were established to test the relationship between them. The first of these equations is Model 1 is to test the effect of the independent variable ATD on the dependent variable ENV; the second one is Model 2 to test the effect of the

independent variable ATD on the mediator variable CTK; and the last one is Model 3 to test the effects of the mediator variable CTK and independent variable ATD on the dependent variable ENV:

$$\text{Model 1: ENV} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{ATD} + \varepsilon \quad (\text{H}_3)$$

$$\text{Model 2: CTK} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{ATD} + \varepsilon \quad (\text{H}_1)$$

$$\text{Model 3: ENV} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{CTK} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{ATD} + \varepsilon \quad (\text{H}_2 \text{ ve } \text{H}_4)$$

4.1. Data

The research was carried out based on data sets of CTK, ATD and ENV indicators. CTK indicator was from World Bank; ATD indicator was from World Economic Forum (WEF); ENV indicator was obtained from Sustainable Society Index (SSI) database. The research analyzed 248 data sets from 62 countries for the years 2010, 2012, 2014 and 2016. Secondary data was used in the research. Since the data was based on objective scales published by international organizations, it deemed not necessary to determine their validity and reliability and therefore confirmatory factor analysis was not needed. This was not a comparative analysis, or an analysis aimed at revealing changes in given time-period. It was a cross sectional analysis to establish the relations between the variables at one point in time. Therefore, the main motivation of the research was restricted to the aim of determining linear relationships based on the selected data sample. Therefore, the period considered was sufficient for the purpose and scope of the study.

4.2. Measurement

CTK is an air traffic indicator and expressed in million tons-km being published by the World Bank. It contains volume of cargo, express and diplomatic bags carried during each flight phase – the operation of an aircraft from takeoff to its next landing – measured in metric tons multiplied by kilometers traveled (one metric ton of cargo carried in one kilometer). For International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) statistical purposes, cargo includes express and diplomatic shipments but excludes passenger baggage. It is based on estimates from the ICAO, World Civil Aviation Statistics, and ICAO staff (IATA,2023).

ATD is an indicator that measures the development of quality, condition, and extensiveness of air transport infrastructure. It is based on the World Economic Forum (WEF) Global Enabling Report, Executive Opinion Survey (EOS). These surveys – answered by industry experts – rank countries as 1=extremely underdeveloped, among the worst in the world; 7=comprehensive and efficient and is evaluated according to a scale among the best in the world (WEF, 2016).

ENV is an indicator that measures environmental sustainability under two main categories. Climate and energy (C&E) – being one of these categories consisting of four sub-indicators published by the International Energy Agency: The first of these is energy use, which shows the use of oil equivalent to tons per capita; the second is energy savings, which shows the percentage change in the four-year use of energy; the third one is greenhouse gases, which shows annual CO₂ emissions per capita; The fourth and the last one consists of renewable energy indicators as a percentage of energy consumption (SSI, 2023).

Natural resources – being the other category consisting of three sub-indicators: The first of these is biodiversity, measured by the ten-year change of forest area and the Environmental Performance Index (EPI), which shows the size of protected land areas as a percentage of a country's total land area; second one, renewable water resources from internal and external neighboring countries, which express the annual water consumption measured by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) to monitor the adequacy and depletion of clean water resources as a percentage of the total available renewable water resources; the third and last one is based on the ecological footprint indicator measured by subtracting the carbon footprint value of the Global Footprint Network (GFN) (SSI, 2023). After defining these indicators to be used in the sample, we can now move on to the analysis.

5. Results and Discussion

Baron & Kenny's (1986) method determined that there should be a significant correlation between the variables as a primary requirement. As such, table 2 shows that there was a significant correlation between the variables:

Table 2: Correlation Coefficients

	ATD	CTK	ENV
ATD	-	.522*	-.444*
CTK	.522*	-	-.410*
ENV	-.444*	-.410*	-

Source: Author (*Correlation is significant at 1%)

After the achievement of significant correlation, the multi collinearity test was also conducted to detect for possible multi-collinearity problem between the independent variables. Multi-collinearity test is based on the values of variance inflation factor and tolerance and the results are expected to be below 10 for the former and above 0.1 for the latter to pass the test. Table 3 shows the test values for the former as 1.376 and for the latter as 0.727, both of which were deemed to be at acceptable level (Keith, 2015:202).

Table 3: Multi collinearity statistics

Independent variables	Dependent variable	Tolerance	VIF
ATD, CTK	ENV	0.727(>0.1)	1.376 (<10)

Source: Author

The research developed three models to test the effect of the mediator variable. Table 4 shows the co-efficient, R², adjusted R² and F statistics values obtained in the regression analysis:

Table 4: Model Regression statistics

Inter-relations	MODEL I	MODEL II	MODEL III
ATD →ENV	-.444*	-	-.316*
ATD →CTK	-	.522*	-
CTK →ENV	-	-	-.245*
R ²	.197	.273	.241
Adjusted R ²	.194	.270	.235
F	60.402*	92.375*	38.837*

Source: Author (*p is significant at 1%)

From table 4 the values reached were statistically significant and this meant that all the following hypotheses were supported:

H₁: Positive effect of ATD on CTK ($\beta_{\text{model II}} = .522$ $p < 0.01$)

H₂: Negative effect of CTK on ENV ($\beta_{\text{model III}} = -.245$, $p < 0.01$)

H₃: Negative effect of ATD on ENV ($\beta_{\text{model I}} = -.444$ $p < 0.01$)

H₄: The mediator variable role of CTK between ATD and ENV ($\beta_{\text{model III}} = -.316$, $p < 0.01$).

The result of the analysis shows that previous significant negative effect of ATD on ENV (-.444) decreased now to -.316 because of the inclusion of CTK in the analysis but continues to be statistically significant. One last step for verification of a mediator effect is the test called Sobel. Table 4 gives the result of the Sobel test based on the unstandardized regression coefficients and their standard errors and the results were also found to be statistically significant (Sobel, 1982). With this result, it was confirmed that CTK was a partial mediator in the relationship between ATD and ENV.

Table 4: Multiple collinearity statistics

	SOBEL Test Statistics	Significance (p value)
ATD →CTK→ENV	-3.59416088	0.00

Source: Author

Therefore, the first hypothesis – testing the direct positive impact of ATD on CTK – was supported. Studies in the literature show that the development of the extensiveness and the condition of air transport infrastructure increase the quality of ATD which in turn positively influences CTK. The test was found to be in line with the literature.

The second hypothesis – testing the direct negative impact of air cargo on environmental sustainability – was supported. More international trade means more CTK which in turn positively influence economic and social wellbeing. And yet increasing level of CTK has an adverse effect on ENV. This outcome is also in line with the research in the literature.

The third hypothesis – testing the direct negative impact of ATD on ENV – was supported. Literature and theory support this outcome. However, it is necessary to distinguish between developments in air transport infrastructure that bring efficiency and large investments that lead to a waste of resources harming environment.

Finally, the fourth hypothesis – testing the mediating role of CTK between ATD and ENV – was supported. While the condition and extensiveness of ATD positively affects CTK, both former and latter also negatively influences ENV. It is compatible with the literature.

6. Conclusions

Air cargo provides fast and reliable transportation and its importance among other modes is increasing. In line with this increasing importance, there are significant growth in cargo traffic carried by air. These increases naturally make the development of air transportation infrastructure a necessity. Large investments in infrastructure to meet the increase in traffic in turn positively affect air cargo, creating a mutually beneficial relationship. Although this relationship positively affects economic and human welfare, it has serious negative effects on environmental sustainability. These adverse effects are especially apparent on natural resources and climate. While increased traffic triggers a higher fossil fuel consumption, large investments to improve the condition and extensiveness of air transportation infrastructure seriously harm natural resources and the environment.

This study investigated therefore to what extent the development of air transport infrastructure affects environmental sustainability and what role air cargo traffic plays in this relationship. The research analyzed 248 cross-sectional data sets and samples of 62 countries for the years 2010, 2012, 2014 and 2016 using the Baron and Kenny mediator variable method, hierarchical regression, and Sobel test. The result showed that air cargo mediates partially in the relationship between air transport development and environmental sustainability: By introducing air cargo in the analysis, the previous negative effect of air transport development on environmental sustainability decreases but its statistical significance continues.

This result signifies that the increase in air cargo traffic and the development of the air transportation infrastructure needs to be considered together as a whole. Policies therefore to improve welfare should strike a balance between the developing infrastructure and the increasing traffic on the one hand, preventing the climate change and protecting the natural resources on the other. These policies first and foremost should encourage efficiency improvements and limit wasteful traffic and expansions. Targets and strategies should be set and be prioritized to serve only to these policy objectives as a first step. Otherwise, the goals of improving economic, human/social welfare would not mean much in an unsustainable environment.

The importance of this study can be seen in two ways. One is that it finds the increase of air cargo traffic and development of air transport – in its condition and extensiveness – having both negative impact on environmental sustainability. Two is that in this relationship air cargo is a partial mediator adversely affecting the environmental sustainability, but not to an extent to be able eliminate the significant negative effect of air transport development completely.

This study was limited in following aspects: First, because the indicator for air transport development was based on executive opinion surveys, it may reflect the subjective opinions of participants. Second, because the study aimed at investigating linear relationships, the time effect was ignored. Therefore, these relationships could further be analyzed in time series studies to see whether any changes have taken place over the years. Additionally, by including economic and social/human sustainability indicators as part of sustainability triple bottom line, this study could be improved and become more comprehensive.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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